

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17

Supplementary Materials for:

***Hair mercury levels, serum n-3 fatty acids, and pregnancy glucose outcomes among women
from a fertility center***

Contents

Table S1. Comparison of baseline characteristics between participants included and excluded from this study.

Table S2. Associations of hair mercury levels with blood glucose during pregnancy, without adjustment.

Table S3. Associations of hair mercury levels with blood glucose during pregnancy stratified by the sum of serum EPA and DHA concentrations.

Table S4. Associations of hair mercury levels with blood glucose during pregnancy stratified by pre-pregnancy BMI.

Figure S1. Correlation between serum EPA+DHA concentrations and hair mercury (Hg) levels.

Figure S2. Correlations between dietary and supplemental n3PUFA intake and serum EPA + DHA concentrations (n=156).

Figure S3. Correlations between fish and supplemental n3PUFA intake and hair mercury (Hg) levels (n=362).

18 **Table S1. Comparison of baseline characteristics between participants included and**
 19 **excluded from this study.**

	Overall	Included	Excluded
N. of participants	841	430	411
Age, years	35.0 [32.0, 38.0]	35.0 [32.0, 38.0]	35.0 [32.0, 39.0]
Body Mass Index, kg/m ²	23.4 [21.2, 26.4]	23.4 [21.3, 26.4]	23.4 [21.1, 26.5]
Race, N (%)			
White/Caucasian	704 (83.7)	361 (84.0)	343 (83.5)
Black/Asian/Other	137 (16.3)	69 (16.0)	68 (16.5)
Graduate degree, N (%)	518 (61.6)	287 (66.7)	231 (56.2)
Ever smoked, N (%)			
Never	634 (75.4)	330 (76.7)	304 (74.0)
Past	189 (22.5)	90 (20.9)	99 (24.1)
Current	18 (2.1)	10 (2.3)	8 (1.9)

20

21 **Table S2. Associations of hair mercury levels with blood glucose during pregnancy,**
 22 **without adjustment.**

Hair mercury levels	GLT blood glucose (mg/dL)		Impaired glucose tolerance (IGT)	
	β (95% CI)	p-value	OR (95% CI)	p-value
Continuous	0.07 (-0.02, 0.16)	0.14	1.20 (0.94, 1.55)	0.15
Quartile				
Q1	Ref.		Ref.	
Q2	0.01 (-0.26, 0.28)	0.94	0.84 (0.41, 1.68)	0.62
Q3	0.01 (-0.26, 0.27)	0.95	1.07 (0.55, 2.10)	0.84
Q4	0.20 (-0.06, 0.47)	0.14	1.82 (0.98, 3.45)	0.061
Trend		0.16		0.038
≥ 1 vs. < 1 ppm	0.10 (-0.10, 0.30)	0.32	1.11 (0.91, 1.35)	0.31

23 Abbreviation: GLT, 1-h non-fasting, 50-gram glucose loading test.

24 **Table S3. Associations of hair mercury levels with blood glucose during pregnancy**
 25 **stratified by the sum of serum EPA and DHA concentrations.**

Hair mercury levels	GLT blood glucose (mg/dL)			Impaired glucose tolerance (IGT)		
	β (95% CI)	p	p-int	OR (95% CI)	p	p-int
Per SD			0.14			0.49
Low EPA+DHA	0.04 (-0.16, 0.23)	0.72		1.24 (0.68, 2.51)	0.52	
High EPA+DHA	0.03 (-0.20, 0.26)	0.78		0.81 (0.34, 2.23)	0.65	
Quartile			0.36			0.67
Low EPA+DHA						
Q1	Ref.			Ref.		
Q2	0.02 (-0.46, 0.51)	0.92		1.43 (0.30, 7.29)	0.65	
Q3	-0.30 (-0.85, 0.26)	0.30		1.24 (0.18, 7.67)	0.82	
Q4	0.28 (-0.29, 0.84)	0.34		2.07 (0.33, 12.74)	0.42	
Trend		0.68			0.48	
High EPA+DHA						
Q1	Ref.			Ref.		
Q2	-0.12 (-0.74, 0.49)	0.69		0.16 (0.01, 2.22)	0.17	
Q3	0.11 (-0.49, 0.71)	0.72		0.31 (0.03, 3.49)	0.32	
Q4	0.05 (-0.56, 0.65)	0.88		1.01 (0.13, 10.39)	0.99	
Trend		0.61			0.47	
≥ 1 vs. < 1 ppm			0.004			0.09
Low EPA+DHA	-0.11 (-0.56, 0.34)	0.64		0.91 (0.19, 3.86)	0.91	
High EPA+DHA	0.20 (-0.16, 0.56)	0.28		4.48 (1.11, 22.00)	0.045	

26 Models were adjusted for maternal age (continuous), pre-pregnancy BMI (continuous),
 27 physical activity (continuous), race (white/others), education level (graduate degree/lower),
 28 smoking status (never/past/current), number of babies (singleton/twins or more), and family
 29 history of T2D (yes/no). Abbreviation: BMI, body mass index; GLT, 1-h non-fasting, 50-gram
 30 glucose loading test; EPA, eicosapentaenoic acid; DHA, docosahexaenoic acid; T2D, type 2
 31 diabetes; p-int, p for interaction.

32 **Table S4. Associations of hair mercury levels with blood glucose during pregnancy**
 33 **stratified by pre-pregnancy BMI.**

Hair mercury levels	GLT blood glucose (mg/dL)			Impaired glucose tolerance (IGT)		
	β (95% CI)	p	p-int	OR (95% CI)	p	p-int
Per SD			0.17			0.038
BMI<25	-0.01 (-0.14, 0.12)	0.90		0.86 (0.62, 1.22)	0.40	
BMI>25	0.16 (0.03, 0.29)	0.018		2.03 (1.30, 3.46)	0.005	
Quartile			0.63			0.11
BMI<25						
Q1	Ref.			Ref.		
Q2	-0.11 (-0.44, 0.21)	0.50		0.44 (0.17, 1.12)	0.09	
Q3	-0.13 (-0.46, 0.19)	0.42		0.64 (0.26, 1.53)	0.32	
Q4	0.08 (-0.25, 0.41)	0.62		1.16 (0.51, 2.70)	0.72	
Trend		0.62			0.53	
BMI>25						
Q1	Ref.			Ref.		
Q2	0.29 (-0.15, 0.73)	0.20		2.46 (0.73, 8.76)	0.15	
Q3	0.22 (-0.20, 0.64)	0.31		2.59 (0.82, 8.94)	0.11	
Q4	0.31 (-0.12, 0.74)	0.16		4.18 (1.35, 14.15)	0.016	
Trend		0.18			0.019	
≥ 1 vs. < 1 ppm			0.85			0.70
BMI<25	0.12 (-0.13, 0.36)	0.35		1.35 (0.70, 2.58)	0.36	
BMI>25	-0.03 (-0.37, 0.31)	0.86		1.52 (0.66, 3.46)	0.31	

34
 35 Models were adjusted for maternal age (continuous), physical activity (continuous), race
 36 (white/others), education level (graduate degree/lower), smoking status (never/past/current),
 37 number of babies (singleton/twins or more), and family history of T2D (yes/no). Abbreviation:
 38 BMI, body mass index; GLT, 1-h non-fasting, 50-gram glucose loading test; T2D, type 2
 39 diabetes; p-int, p for interaction.

41

42 **Figure S1. Correlation between serum EPA+DHA concentrations and hair mercury (Hg)**
43 **levels.** (A) Primary analysis including all participants. (B) Sensitivity analysis excluding six
44 women with extremely high EPA+DHA concentrations.

45

46

Figure S2. Correlations between dietary and supplemental n3PUFA intake and serum

47

EPA + DHA concentrations (n=156). Total n3PUFA intake included n3PUFA from both food

48

and supplements.

49

50

51

Figure S3. Correlations between fish and supplemental n3PUFA intake and hair mercury (Hg) levels (n=362).